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"THE OUTSOURCING DECISION IN FUZZY ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENTS"

By

Enrique López-González

Cristina Mendaña Cuervo

Departamento de Dirección y Economía de la Empresa

Universidad de León. Campus de Vegazana, s/n

E- 24071 León (España)

Phone: inter + 34.87.291742

Fax: inter + 34.87.291454

The new competitive dynamic of business has put in question the benefits of vertical integration, compelling to managers to be interested in flexible-modular organizations and to focus their attention on those internal operations of essential activities which due to knowledge, abilities, culture, etc., give a sustaining advantage, whilst the now essential services are done by external firms which offer advantages in costs, flexibility and access, its resources, skills and latest technologic advances.

Accountants can play an important role in deciding which activities should be bought externally. An important question arises, however, in determining the correct methodology for helping managers make such strategic outsourcing decisions.

Thus, facing the inherent uncertainty to the new competitive dynamic which characterizes the economic environment, plus the proper uncertainty of future planification, it is questioned in our paper the necessity of applying the Fuzzy Subsets Theory in order to allow the treatment of accountant information for the outsourcing strategy in competitive markets.

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Fuzzy Method Applied to Airbrone

Multi-Sensor Multi-Target Tracking System

Prof. Zhang Yi-dle

XIOlan University, Xi'an. P.R.China

Tracking of maneuvering outltarget in clutter is a very difficult task and especially the task of * Plot-Track Association *. Generally this task is mainly performed by using the kinematic data of the targets measured by a surveillance radar or/and other sensors. Although many association and tracking algorithms have been suggested, but in dense clutter environment it is still difficult to generating and maintaining tracks with low false-alarm rate, in fact, this problem is a typical * Objects Classification and identification ' problem-to identify which one of the returns within the correlation gate is coming from the 'old' target.

Based on this point of view. In our work, not only the dynamic behaviors but also the attributes of the targets are used. Because some of the attributes are relied upon the position, gesture and shape of the targets, these attributes are normalized firstly. And combined with some of the kinematic data of the returns, such as velocity and height, these attributes are used to classify the returns into two parts: false returns formed by clutter and noise, and 'true' returns from targets, then the next step is identify which one of these

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(Paper for debate)

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Enrique López-González
Cristina Mendaña Cuervo

Departamento de Dirección y Economía de la Empresa
Universidad de León. Campus de Vegazana, s/n
E- 24071 León (España)
Phone: inter + 34.87.291742
Fax: inter + 34.87.291454

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Summary

The new competitive dynamic of business has put in question the benefits of vertical integration, compelling to managers to be interested in flexible-modular organizations and to focus their attention on those internal operations of essential activities which due to knowledge, abilities, culture, etc., give a sustaining advantage, whilst the now essential services are done by external firms which offer advantages in costs, flexibility and access to resources, skills and latest technologic advances.

Accountants can play an important role in deciding which activities should be bought externally. An important question arises, however, in determining the correct methodology for helping managers make such strategic outsourcing decisions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The present paper is focused on the pushing forces that explain the transition of the business organizations from the productivity paradigm to the one based on the searching of competitive advantages which characterize the actual economic environment. That analysis could let us know, in second place, the implications of such evolution in the Management Accounting, appearing the concept of Strategic Management Accounting, which may perform an important role in the present economic environment, providing the necessary information to get competitive advantages, through the application of all kind of mathematic models allowing both the anticipation to the future and the evaluation of alternative courses of action.

Thus, facing the inherent uncertainty to the new competitive dynamic which characterizes the environment, plus the proper uncertainty of future planification, it is questioned the necessity of applying the Fuzzy Subsets Theory in order to allow the treatment of accountant information for the strategy in competitive markets.

2. AN FUZZY ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT: THE NEW COMPETITIVE DYNAMIC

The new competitive dynamic has put in question the benefits of vertical integration [Tully, 1993, pp. 52], compelling to manager to be interested in organizations flexible and to focus their attention in those internal operations of essential activities which due to knowledge, abilities, culture, etc., give a sustaining advantage, whilst the non essential services are done by external firms which offer advantages in costs, flexibility and access to resources, skills and the latest technologic advances.

The first answers of the firms facing the exigences of the new competitive dynamic have consisted basically in movements of desarticulation disgregation of activities and the technological and industrial recentering.

Talking about the first mentioned aspect, it may be observed how the technological unfreezing originated by the fordist model desarticulate the set of elements which configurated the productive systems highly structured and highly efficient. In this way, the raw materials, the equipment, the work force, the suppliers and the customers might be separated to give place to changes, innovations, new distribution of the work, etc. moving from the standarization of the product to the standarization of the components and, therefore, to the maximun exploitation of the possibilities of the process [De la Puerta, 1992, p. 394]. Thus, the target of attention is not based already on the large volume production based on economies of scale but better in more specific products adapted to the customer needs (Activity Based Management).

Besides, the firms are focused in those internal operations of a little set of critic activities, reforsing those non essential services which are bought to external agents since they can offer costs advantages, flexibility and the access to the latest associated technological advances, i.e., the firms begin a technological and industrial process of recentering, incrementing, by other hand, the degree of externalization (outsourcing) of the needed activities to get the final product [Peters, 1992]. In this way, the "cooperation's management" becomes a fundamental factor to compete in this new economic environment, standing out them the magnitude of "make or buy" decisions and the necessity of strategic alliances [Bleeke and Ernst, 1993]. This is like that insofar as the main focus of interest is not the competitiveness by itself but that it is been competing to maximize the creation of value for customer, this is, the objective is the customer and not the competitor: instead of focusing on the competitor as an enemy the emerging management is centred on the customer as a company partner [Stahl and Bounds, 1993].

On the other hand, the scientifics are looking for new schemes capable to make a new treatment of those new situations as the schemes that traditionally give the economic studies, with base on certainty and probability, although they are still valid in many circumstances, they don't manage to reflect this new dynamic based on the uncertainty.

3. UNCERTAINTY AND STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING

The simple study developed in the previous epigraph has allowed us to verify how a "Fordism" organization is oriented to productivity, considering constant the value that the product or services performance qualities have for customers (an standard manufactured in large mass production whose modification means enormous costs) and treating then only to reduce the costs of such performance qualities. On the contrary, the flexible, horizontal or projects' organizations, are oriented to achieve competitive advantages, trying to introduce those necessary changes to maximize the value for the customer.

This transition from productivity to competitiveness has implications on the role that the Management Accounting has to perform, defined as: "the accountant science working through its models on a specific economic management system and, inside it, supplying useful information to the economic system" [García García and Ucieda Arcas, 1992, pp. 24].

In this sense some authors [among others, Kaplan, 1983; Cooper and Kaplan, 1987; Berliner and Brimson, 1988] have suggested a reform of the managerial accountancy, arguing the necessity that is has to be oriented to facilitate a continuous improvement and a total quality control, having then to treat each activity as a process and to identify the costs "source" more than worrying only about the "symptoms".

Nevertheless, in the new competitive dynamic, it is not enough to focuss the attention on the control of activities, it is been required to have in mind the products or services' performance qualities that they provide to their users. In consequence, and given that the first reason of the existence of the managerial accountancy inside the firms lies in that it allows the development and the application of the strategy inside them, some authors [among others, Simmonds, 1981; Shank and Govindarajan, 1989; Bromwich, 1990; Ward, 1992] have suggested the new concept of Strategic Management Accounting.

A working definition of Strategic Management Accounting formulated by Bromwich is: "The prevision and analysis of financial information on the firm's product markets and competitors costs and cost structures and the monitoring of the enterprise's strategies and those of its competitors in those markets over a number of periods" [Bromwich, 1990, pp. 28].

Thus, the material objective of the strategic accountancy will be given by the managerial reality as a whole, and its formal objective will be established by the treatment and analysis of accountant information for the firm's strategy facing competitive markets, that is to say, to facillitate the search of competitive advantages.

To carry out is objectives the strategic accountancy will be able to use all those technics or mathematic instruments capable of allowing a better identification and collection of economic events to formalize them and then to be able to operate with them.

This identification and data collection from the reality has traditionally taken place through reasoning based on the concept of precision and whose consequence has been the formalization of a "modified reality", adapted to such mathematic models, instead of exactly the opposite thing, i.e., and adaptation of the said models to the real facts.

About this we can see how the traditional Sets Theory and the Boolean Algebra, with its belong or not belong logic, has allowed the formalization of certain situations that reality shows, but there are others which are difficult to put in a model through this schemes. In fact, facing the necessity of accountant information for the search of competitive advantages, problems arise which require the taking of decisions about the nature's state (in question), the objectives that are been tried to reach, and even the consequences of the possible actions are not knowed with precision and the notion of probability is not suitable to describe the said reality, because it is necessary to do tasks of representation, collecting and comparison of imprecise, vague or linguistic information.

The probability deals with a special kind of uncertainty, the randomness, and this kind of uncertainty is objective, i.e., it refers to experiments which are not depending on the person that undertakes them. On the other hand, in our field of study, it results very difficult that a phenomenon should be repeated an enough number of times for the probability to be introduced with validity.

Nevertheless, in the attempts to formalize the current firms' behaviour and economic activities has result each time more necessary to incorporate hypothesis than even when they are not measurables they are capable of estimation, comparison and gradation, relation, etc., seeing that if a situation cannot be specified but it can be stated that it is better than another one we pass to a superior stage of knowledge, this is, when it is said that a future happening is more "possible" than another a fundamental field in the perspectives of reasoning and decision is being opened, since the subjective knowledge may be yield, almost, to all the mecanisms of logic.

Thus, if our environment knowledge is imprecise, as it happes on the taking of managerial decisions, the mathematic tool which the Strategic Management Accounting has to work with, in order to facillitate the said taking of decisions, must include the notion of level of presumption.

The Fuzzy figures (o numbers) have been created to reflect the vagueness of human perception and with that the notion of level of confidence (presumption). In this way, the Fuzzy Subsets Theory, as a branch of Mathematics which deals with the treatment of both the subjective and the uncertain, constitute an attempt to collect a phenomenon as it is exactly in reality and to do its threatment without trying its deformation to do it precise and certain [Zadeh, 1965]. As the firms' responsible managers recognize that their environment is fuzzy or uncertain it becomes evident that they preffer realist representations but imprecise opposite to models only supposedly exact.

The Fuzzy Subsets Theory applied in Biology, Medicine, etc., maybe specially useful as for the treatment of uncertainty in business management is concerned [among others Gil Lafuente, 1993; Kaufmann y Gil Aluja, 1986, 1987, 1991, 1992, 1993; López González y Mendaña Cuervo, 1992; Teodorescu, Yamakawa y Rascanu, 1992; Tofan et al., 1992; Zimmerman, 1983].

The following paragraph is a try of application of fuzzy systems for the treatment of decisiones

of outsourcing arise by the technological and industrial recentering to whom the firms react facing the new competitive dynamic cited before.

4. AN CASE OF THE FUZZY STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING: THE OUTSOURCING DECISION

The subcontractation theme and, hence, the role that accounting information may play in order to facilitate the buy or make (outsourcing) decision, might be considered as a topic in the accounting literature [among others, Anderson et al., 1989; Horngren, Foster and Datar, 1994; Liao and Book, 1989; Moriarity and Allen, 1987; Moscovice and Wright, 1990; Morse and Roth, 1986; Polimeni et al., 1991; Rayburn, 1987; Usry et al., 1988], where normally its discussion developed in a fabrication context and insisting on the importance of differential and opportunity costs in the calculus of make or buy decision analysis.

This analysis has been traditionally posed from a short term perspective, being centered in the best use of available capacities [for instance Horngren, Foster and Datar, 1994, pp. 394-400], and in the acquisition of parts or components, this is, the decision is limited, in most of the managerial accountancy books, to the effects on the differential results only on the corresponding year.

In the said analysis, in order to evaluate such decision in an appropriate form, the components' standards of quality and quantity must be equal to both alternative courses. In relation to the qualitative factors diverse aspects must be studied as, for instance, technological innovation, trade secrets, product quality, seasonal sale figures, relations with suppliers and fluctuations in the production.

About the quantitative factors, the determination of relevant costs to buy means to have in mind the inclusion of all the costs of offering in the same conditions, physical and location, as it would be made internally and not only the acquisition price. At the same time the alternative of make relevant costs must include all the which such production involves, in addition to examine the associated opportunity costs facing the possibility of alternative use of idle capacities.

Nevertheless, the previous considerations, with the emphasis on the short term, are far to be completely valid in the present economic context where the make or buy decision is posed necessarily from a wider point of view, which needs to have into account the long term effects linked in such decision.

In the present scene the efficient use of the firm's assets is an important factor to get a competitive advantage, although it is not an aim by itself but that must be integrated inside the organization's global plan which may allow the development of the own competences, as the interest relies in that the responsible managers should be focused in those few activities or business segments which are understood and done correctly and which the competitors can hardly reproduce [Drina, 1993].

In this way, faced with the necessity to have the enough flexibility to give a quick answer to the customer requests, a strategy focused in the fundamental activities will give to the organization some operative unique or particular (competitive advantages) characteristics when they are combined with the subcontractation of those services which the firm cannot execute on a comparable level with the best world's organizations.

The decision process of subcontracting, according to **Exhibit 1** would be then the following: the first step would consist in to recognize and to understand the firm's "chain of value" and the iterations among the different activities. From the identification of those activities capable of subcontracting three main thoughts are questioned: the first question that may be posed is whether the firm needs a total control of such activity or not. Finally, whether the firm is capable to execute the said service or to access to the resources [Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978] as the best of the world (benchmarking).

According to the previous observations the Strategic Management Accounting may perform an important role in the decision of making internally the activity or to buy from external sources. Specifically, an accountant statement could be elaborated which would deal with an enough number of years, five at least, and where it could be analysed the relevant differential costs in the decision. In fact, as in any other long term decision, the acceptance criterion must not be restricted to the perspective of differential cost among the alternative action courses along the planification horizon, but it must be based upon the discounted cash-flows, this is, the value of time must be considered. For this, the total costs of doing internally and those of external subcontracting of the questioned service are transformed in cash flows and, then, the difference between the cash flows originated if the service is done inside the firm and the cash necessities required for the external acquisition allows to obtain the differential annual cash flow if the said subcontracting is carried out.

In this way, using the actualization technique, a series of available amounts of cash in different times may be reduced to a single value, the discounted cash flow (net present value) and to solve then the "preference order" of the alternative actions.

As an illustrative example suppose the following example: a telecommunications firm is questioning the maintenance of its fleet of vehicles relating with the installation of new lines and telephone sets, because it could be interesting to outsource that service, avoiding then the collection of many vehicles and means of transportation.

In this sense, **Exhibit 2** shows, on a five years horizon, what would it be, in first place, the convenient state to be elaborated for the make or buy decision. In a way that if only the short term were considered for the decision, and given the outsourcing differential savings by 7.800 monetary units, the subcontracting (outsourcing) would be the option for that maintenance service. However considering a minimum 5 years period of time, where the total incidence of such project would be better observed, it is visible that such decision would mean a loss of 3.900 monetary units.

Nevertheless, the inclusion of the value of money through the time, poses the necessity to elaborate **Exhibit 3** which stands for the classic actualization formula. In this Exhibit it can be observed then that if the outsourcing decision is taken, according to its net present value, a profit of 1.083'85 m.u. would be taken, contradicting the previous decision which not considering the value of money throughout the time, it supposed the existence of a loss of 3.900 u.m.

On the other hand, and according with the observations developed in the third paragraph, it is convenient to take into account that the previous considerations are developed under the perfect hypothesis (certainty environment) where both, the amount of the net cash flows and the annual interest rates in the planification period, are supposed to be known, but such premise results to be hardly admissible in the present environment characterized by the uncertainty, which carries

the necessity of make subjective evaluations, thus the importance that the subjective aspects have in the make or buy decision as it can be contrasted in any empiric investigation related with this area [Gambino, 1980, pp. 9-10].

In this sense, "the opening of new perspectives in the mathematic field has allowed to give an orientation renewed to the usable economic techniques in the field of investments. It is available for that, in addition to the classics elements, the possible systematic use of the Fuzzy Subsets Theory which may give to this studies the necessary impulse to adapt them to the necessities of a real world each time more immerse in the field of uncertainty" [Kaufmann and Gil Aluja, 1986, pp. 71].

In this paper, duets its objective, we will focus particularly in the fuzzy numbers applied to the actualization rates, because the determination of a single interest rate means, formally, the existence of a perfect capital market and that the calculated interest rate corresponds to the balance between supply and offer of capitals. Such hypothesis is difficult to admit in the reality, where a wide range of rates exists depending on both the moment and the corresponding business.

According to the previous, in an illustrative way, we can suppose that a group of experts have reached agreement for three values of the rate of actualization i for each time t in planificate period corresponding to the make or buy decision: the lower will be r , the level of confidence, will be m , while the upper value will be s , this is, it has been accepted a triangular fuzzy number to describe the uncertain value i , as it is represented in the **Exhibit 4**. In this Exhibit it can be observed that to every level $0 \leq \alpha_k \leq 1$ a "confidence interval" $[r_k^{(\alpha)}, s_k^{(\alpha)}]$ appears which is possible to express in function of α_k , in the following way:

$$[r_k^{(a)}, s_k^{(a)}] = [r + (m - r) \cdot \alpha_k, s - (s - m) \cdot \alpha_k]$$

In fact, by similarity of triangles:

$$x = \frac{m - r}{1 - \alpha_k} \cdot \alpha_k$$

and in the same way,

$$y = \frac{s - m}{\alpha_k} \cdot \alpha_k$$

At the same time, and as it is already known, from the confidence intervals the following operations may be done:

$$\begin{aligned} [a, b] (+) [c, d] &= [a + c, b + d] \\ [a, b] (-) [c, d] &= [a - d, b - c] \\ [a, b] (\cdot) [c, d] &= [a \cdot c, b \cdot d] \\ & a, b, c, d, \in \mathbb{R}^+ \\ [a, b] (:) [c, d] &= [a / d, b / c] \\ & a, b, c, d, \in \mathbb{R}^+ \text{ y } c > 0 \\ [1, 1] (:) [c, d] &= [1 / d, 1 / c] \end{aligned}$$

$$c, d \in \mathbb{R}^+ \text{ y } c > 0$$

which allows to write the actualization rate in fuzzy form, as it follows:

$$\frac{1}{1 + [r_k^{(a)}, s_k^{(a)}]} = \frac{1}{[1 + r_k^{(a)}, 1 + s_k^{(a)}]} = \left[\frac{1}{1 + s_k^{(a)}}, \frac{1}{1 + r_k^{(a)}} \right]$$

In this way, if the known actualization formula for n number of periods (taking the year as a period), is the following:

$$V_n = A_0 + A_1 \cdot (1+i)^{-1} + A_2 \cdot (1+i)^{-2} + \dots + A_n \cdot (1+i)^{-n}$$

where A_j is the year j cash flow and V_n the cash flows actualized along the n periods.

Then, the formulation of the actualization for the five periods mentioned in the previous example, but now including uncertain data (triangular fuzzy numbers), will be as it following page. This expression allows to get, for each level α , the range of possibilities where it is likely to find the real outcome (result) as well as the corresponding value to the highest presumption.

Thus, the **Exhibit 5** and **Exhibit 6** shows the outsourcing decision in an fuzzy economic environment.

$$\begin{aligned}
VAN_5 = & \left[\frac{A_1^{(1)} + (A_2^{(2)} - A_1^{(1)}) a}{(1 + s_1 - (s_1 - m_1) a)}, \frac{A_3^{(1)} - (A_3^{(1)} - A_2^{(1)}) a}{(1 + r_1 + (m_1 - r_1) a)} \right] + \\
& + \left[\frac{A_1^{(2)} + (A_2^{(2)} - A_1^{(2)}) a}{(1 + s_1 - (s_1 - m_1) a) \bullet (1 - s_2 - (s_2 - m_2) a)}, \frac{A_3^{(2)} - (A_3^{(2)} - A_2^{(2)}) a}{(1 + r_1 + (m_1 - r_1) a) \bullet (1 + r_2 + (m_2 - r_2) a)} \right] + \\
& + \left[\frac{A_1^{(3)} + (A_2^{(3)} - A_1^{(3)}) a}{(1 + s_1 - (s_1 - m_1) a) \bullet (1 - s_2 - (s_2 - m_2) a) \bullet (1 + s_3 - (s_3 - m_3) a)}, \frac{A_3^{(3)} - (A_3^{(3)} - A_2^{(3)}) a}{(1 + r_1 + (m_1 - r_1) a) \bullet (1 + r_2 + (m_2 - r_2) a) \bullet (1 + r_3 + (m_3 - r_3) a)} \right] + \\
& + \left[\frac{A_1^{(4)} + (A_2^{(4)} - A_1^{(4)}) a}{(1 + s_1 - (s_1 - m_1) a) \bullet (1 - s_2 - (s_2 - m_2) a) \bullet (1 + s_3 - (s_3 - m_3) a) \bullet (1 + s_4 - (s_4 - m_4) a)}, \frac{A_3^{(4)} - (A_3^{(4)} - A_2^{(4)}) a}{(1 + r_1 + (m_1 - r_1) a) \bullet (1 + r_2 + (m_2 - r_2) a) \bullet (1 + r_3 + (m_3 - r_3) a) \bullet (1 + r_4 + (m_4 - r_4) a)} \right] + \\
& + \left[\frac{A_1^{(5)} + (A_2^{(5)} - A_1^{(5)}) a}{(1 + s_1 - (s_1 - m_1) a) \bullet (1 - s_2 - (s_2 - m_2) a) \bullet (1 + s_3 - (s_3 - m_3) a) \bullet (1 + s_4 - (s_4 - m_4) a) \bullet (1 + s_5 - (s_5 - m_5) a)}, \frac{A_3^{(5)} - (A_3^{(5)} - A_2^{(5)}) a}{(1 + r_1 + (m_1 - r_1) a) \bullet (1 + r_2 + (m_2 - r_2) a) \bullet (1 + r_3 + (m_3 - r_3) a) \bullet (1 + r_4 + (m_4 - r_4) a) \bullet (1 + r_5 + (m_5 - r_5) a)} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Exhibit 1. Steps in the Outsourcing Decision Analysis [Drtina, 1993]

MAKE OPTION: SERVICE VEHICLES IN-HOUSE					
	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5
Vehicles per year	600	625	650	675	700
Variable costs/vehicle	470	470	470	470	470
Total variable costs	282,000	293,750	305,500	317,250	329,000
Payroll and training	102,000	102,000	110,500	110,500	119,000
Facilities-utilities, maintenance	15,000	15,000	15,000	15,000	15,000
Facilities-depreciation	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000
Fixed costs/per year	147,000	147,000	155,500	155,500	164,000
Total costs	429,000	440,750	461,000	472,750	493,000
Less tax effect (@ 35%)	150,150	154,262	161,350	165,462	172,550
Net cost of servicing vehicles in-house	278,850	286,487	299,650	307,287	320,450

Exhibit 2

BUY OPTION: OUTSOURCE VEHICLE SERVICE					
	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5
Vehicles per year	600	625	650	675	700
Service costs per vehicle	870	870	870	870	870
Total contractual costs	522,000	543,750	565,500	587,250	609,000
Facilities-depreciation	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000
Total operating costs	552,000	573,750	595,500	617,250	639,000
Less opportunity cost rental revenue	135,000	135,000	135,000	135,000	135,000
Total costs	417,000	438,750	460,500	482,250	504,000
Less tax effect (@ 35%)	145,950	153,562	161,175	168,787	176,400
Net cost of outsourcing vehicle maintenance	271,050	285,187	299,325	313,462	327,600
THE MAKE-BUY DECISION					
Differential cost to outsource	7,800	1,300	325	- 6,175	- 7,150
Total differential cost	- 3,900				

Exhibit 2 (cont.)

DISCOUNTED CASH FLOW TO OUTSOURCE FLEET MAINTENANCE CALCULATED						
	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5	
Net cost of outsourcing vehicle maintenance	278,850	286,487	299,650	307,287	320,450	
Add back depreciation	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	
Net cash-outflow to outsource	308,850	316,487	329,650	337,287	350,450	
Less net cost of service vehicles in-house	271,050	285,187	299,325	313,462	327,600	
Add back depreciation	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	
Net cost to service in-house	301,050	315,187	329,325	343,462	357,600	
Annual cash differential if outsourced	7,800	1,300	325	- 6,175	- 7,150	
Discounted cash flows (discount factor 16%)	6,724	966	208	- 3,410	- 3,404	
Net present value	1,083,85					

Exhibit 3

MAKE OPTION: SERVICE VEHICLES IN-HOUSE					
	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5
Vehicles per year	[575, 600, 625]	[600, 625, 650]	[625, 650, 675]	[650, 675, 700]	[675, 700, 725]
Variable costs/vehicle	[450, 470, 490]	[470, 490, 510]	[490, 510, 530]	[510, 530, 550]	[530, 550, 580]
Total variable costs	[258,750, 282,000, 306,250]	[282,000, 306,250, 331,500]	[306,350, 331,500, 357,750]	[331,500, 357,750, 385,000]	[357,750, 385,000, 420,500]
Payroll and training	[100,000, 125,000, 150,000]	[125,000, 150,000, 175,000]	[150,000, 175,000, 200,000]	[175,000, 200,000, 225,000]	[200,000, 225,000, 250,000]
Facilities-utilities, maintenance	[10,000, 12,500, 15,000]	[12,500, 15,000, 17,500]	[15,000, 17,500, 20,000]	[17,500, 20,000, 22,500]	[20,000, 22,500, 25,000]
Facilities-depreciation	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000
Fixed costs/per year	140,000, 167,500, 195,000]	[167,500, 195,000, 222,500]	[195,000, 222,500, 250,000]	[222,500, 250,000, 277,500]	[220,000, 277,500, 275,000]
Total costs	[398,750, 449,500, 501,350]	[449,500, 501,250, 554,000]	[501,250, 554,000, 607,750]	[554,000, 607,750, 662,500]	[577,750, 662,500, 695,500]
Less tax effect (@ 35%)	[139,562, 157,325, 175,437]	[157,325, 175,437, 193,900]	[175,437, 193,900, 212,712]	[193,900, 212,712, 231,875]	[202,212, 231,875, 243,420]
Net costs of servicing vehicles in-house	[223,312, 292,175, 361,687]	[255,600, 325,812, 396,675]	[288,537, 360,100, 432,312]	[322,125, 395,037, 468,600]	[334,325, 430,625, 493,280]

Exhibit 5

BUY OPTION: OUTSOURCE VEHICLE SERVICE					
	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5
Vehicles per year	[575, 600, 625]	[600, 625, 650]	[625, 650, 675]	[650, 675, 700]	[675, 700, 725]

Service cost per vehicle	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
Total contractual costs	[500.250, 522.000, 543.750]	[522.000, 543.750, 565.500]	[543.750, 565.500, 587.250]	[565.500, 587.250, 609.000]	[587.250, 609.000, 66		
Facilities-depreciation	30.000]	30.000	30.000	30.000	30.000		
Total operating costs	[530.250, 552.000, 573.750]	[552.000, 573.750, 595.500]	[573.750, 595.500, 617.250]	[595.500, 617.250, 639.000]	[617.250, 639.000, 66		
Less opportunity cost rental revenue	135.000	135.000	135.000	135.000	135.000		
Total costs	[395.250, 417.000, 438.750]	[417.000, 438.750, 460.500]	[438.750, 460.500, 482.250]	[460.500, 482.250, 504.000]	[482.250, 504.000, 52		
Less tax effect (@ 35%)	[138.337, 145.950, 153.562]	[145.950, 153.562, 161.175]	[161.175, 168.787]	[168.787, 176.400]	[176.400, 18		
Net costs outsourcing vehicle maintenance	[241.687, 271.050, 300.412]	[255.825, 285.187, 314.550]	[269.962, 299.325, 328.687]	[284.100, 313.462, 342.825]	[298.237, 327.600, 35		
Differential costs to outsource	[-77.100, 21.125, 120.000]	[-58.950, 40.625, 140.850]	[-40.150, 60.775, 162.350]	[-20.700, 81.575, 184.500]	[-22.637, 103.025, 195		

Exhibit 5 (cont.)

DISCOUNTED CASH FLOW TO OUTSOURCE FLEET MAINTENANCE CALCULATED					
	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5
Net costs of outsourcing vehicle maintenance	[223.312, 292.175, 361.687]	[255.600, 325.812, 396.675]	[288.537, 360.100, 432.312]	[322.125, 395.037, 468.600]	[334.325, 430.625, 49
Add back depreciation					

	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000
Net cash outflow to outsource	[253,312, 322,175, 391,687]	[285,600, 355,812, 426,675]	[318,537, 390,100, 462,312]	[352,125, 425,037, 498,600]	[364,325, 460,625, 52	
Less net cost of servicing vehicles in-house	[241,687, 271,050, 300,412]	[255,825, 285,187, 314,550]	[269,962, 299,325, 328,687]	[284,100, 313,462, 342,825]	[298,237, 327,600, 35	
Add back depreciation	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	
Net cost to service in-house	[271,687, 301,050, 330,412]	[285,825, 315,187, 344,550]	[299,962, 329,325, 358,687]	[314,100, 343,462, 372,825]	[328,237, 357,600, 38	
Annual cash differential if outsourced	[-77,100, 21,125, 120,000]	[-58,950, 40,625, 140,850]	[-40,150, 60,775, 162,350]	[-20,700, 81,575, 184,500]	[-22,637, 103,025, 19	
Discount factor	[0'08, 0'1, 0'12]	[0'09, 0'12, 0'15]	[0'09, 0'12, 0'15]	[0'08, 0'09, 0'1]	[0'08, 0'09, 0'1	
Discounted cash flows	[-68,839, 19,204, 111,111]	[-45,768, 32,974, 119,848]	[-27,106, 44,045, 126,525]	[-12,705, 54,237, 133,136]	[-12,631, 62,843, 13	
Net present value	[94,740, 213,305, 489,201]					

Exhibit 6